

Radial radio number of chess board graph and king's graph

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ABSTRACT

A radial radio labeling τ of a connected graph $G = (V, E)$ with radius $rad(G)$ is a mapping from $V(G)$ to $N \cup \{0\}$ satisfying $|\tau(u) - \tau(w)| + d(u, w) \geq 1 + rad(G)$, $\forall u, w \in V(G)$. The span of a radial radio labeling τ , denoted by $rr(\tau)$ is the greatest number in the range of τ . The minimum span taken over all radial radio labelings τ of G is called the radial radio number of G and it is denoted by $rr(G)$. In this article, we have investigated the upper bounds for $rr(G)$ of chess board graphs and king's graph.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, our world has been transformed into a higher dimension by digital technology, especially in the field of communication technology. In the beginning of the 21st century, Chartrand *et al.* [1] were motivated by the maximum channel allocation in a fixed spectrum introduced the concept of radio k -chromatic number in graph theory. For any k lies between 1 and the diameter of G , the radio k -chromatic number is defined as follows: Let $G = (V, E)$ be connected graph and d be its diameter, then a radio k -coloring τ of graph G is an assignment of $V(G)$ to non-negative integers such that $|\tau(u) - \tau(w)| + d(u, w) \geq 1 + k$, $\forall u, w \in V(G)$, where $d(u, w)$ is the distance between u and w in G . The span of a radio k -chromatic number of h denoted by $r_{ck}(\tau)$ is the largest number in the range of τ . The radio k -chromatic number of G is the minimum value taken over all such radio k -chromatic number of τ . For different k values, different names were given to the radio k -chromatic number by the researchers in the recent research articles. Namely, when the k values 1 and 2, then the problem is called the chromatic number and $L(2, 1)$ labeling number respectively. Chang and Kue [2] introduced the $L(2, 1)$ -labeling of graphs. Hasunuma *et al.* [3] derived a linear time algorithm for $L(2, 1)$ labeling of trees. Yenoke *et al.* [4], [5] determined the upper bound for the $L(2, 1)$ problem of slim tree, comb graph, double comb graph and Christmas tree, silicate and oxide networks

as 8, 6, 7, 8, 10 and 8 respectively. Prajapati and Patel [6] obtained the $L(2, 1)$ labeling number of crown graph and line graph of armed crown graph. Smitha and Thirusangu [7] determined the $L(2, 1)$ labeling of cycle related graphs. Besides, $L(2, 1)$ labeling of unigraph was computed by Calamoneri and Petreschi [8].

If we vary the value of k as 3, then the problem is named as $L(3, 2, 1)$ labelling. Xavier *et al.* [9] obtained the bounds for the $L(3, 2, 1)$ labelling number of for both n -star graph $S(n, r)$ and n -star-wheel graph $SW(n, r)$ as $2r + 2n + 1$ and n -wheel star graph $WS(n, r)$ as $3r + 2n$. Kim *et al.* [10] solved the $L(3, 2, 1)$ labeling problem the product of C_n and K_n . Moreover, Amanathulla and Pal [11] studied the same on interval graphs. Further, when k reaches the maximum value d , this problem insistence the assigning of channels to FM radio stations called radio labeling problem which was introduced by Chartrand [12]. Rajan *et al.* [13] and Rajan and Yenoke [14] obtained the lower bound for the radio number of any connected graph and also investigated the exact radio number of wheel graph W_{n+1} , double fan graph DF_n , fan graph F_n , windmill graph K_n^m , star graph S_{n+1} and uniform r -cyclic split graph $KC(r)$ as $n + 2, n + 3, n + 2, m(n - 1) + 2, n + 3$ and $nkr + 3n - 2$ respectively.

Vaidya and Bantva [15] attained the exact radio number of the total graph of path P_n for $n = 2k$ and $n = 2k + 1$ as $4k(k - 1) + 2$ and $4k^2 + 3$ respectively. Recently, Yenoke and Kaabar [16] investigated the bounds for the Nanostar tree dendrimer $T_{n,p}(n, p > 2)$ as $rn(T_{n,p}) \leq n + (2n - 1)p + 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (2l - 1)p((p - 1)^{n-l-1})(p - 2) + (2l - 1)p(p)^{n-l-1} - 1$, whenever $p \geq 2n - 3$ and $p(\frac{(p-1)^n - 1}{p-2}) + n + (\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} 2(2n - (2n - i))p(p - 1)^{n-i-1})$ respectively. In addition, when $k = d - 1$, it was named as antipodal radio number by [17], [18]. William and Kenneth [19] investigated the bounds for the antipodal radio number of lobster graph as $an(L(m, r, k)) \leq 24r + 20k - 7$. Saha and Panigrahi [20] studied the same problem for some powers of cycles. Avadayappan *et al.* [21] were introduced the radial radio labeling by fixing the k value as the radius of the graph.

A radial radio labeling ∇ of a connected graph $G = (V, E)$ with radius $rad(G)$ is a mapping from $V(G)$ to $N \cup \{0\}$ satisfying $|\nabla(u) - \nabla(w)| + d(u, w) \geq 1 + rad(G), \forall u, w \in V(G)$. The span of a radial radio labeling ∇ , denoted by $rr(\nabla)$ is the greatest number in the range of ∇ . The minimum span taken over all radial radio labelings ∇ of G is called the radial radio number of G and it is denoted by $rr(G)$. This problem is very helpful in dividing a network into sub networks and to apply the radio labeling conditions in assigning the channels for a particular divided geographical area. Especially, if there is a need of partitioning the existing network into two sub networks, this labeling technique can be applied without affecting the optimal channel assignment.

Hence this method is either used to increase the number of channels or can be used for the same frequency allocation in different geographical area. Since this problem was recently introduced in 2019, only few research articles were published. Avadayappan *et al.* [21], [22] were proved the following significant results: (i) For any simple connected graph $G, rr(G) \geq \omega(G)$. (ii) For any graph G with $m \geq 1$, there is a graph G with $\omega = 3$ and $rr(G) = m + \omega$ (iii) For any graph G with $\omega \geq 4$, there exists a graph G with $rr(G) = \omega + 1$. (iv) For any self centered graph $rr(G) \geq n$, where $n = V(G)$. Yenoke [23] investigated $rr(G)$ of certain uniform cyclic and wheel split graphs as $rr(KDW(r)) \leq 3(r + 2n), n > 4, rr(HW(r)) \leq 2(r + n) + 2, n > 3, rr(SW(r)) \leq 2r + 3n, n > 1, r(KC(r)) = mr + 2n - 2, m > 1$ and $rr(KW(r)) \leq 2r + 4(n - 1), n > 1$.

Recently, Jose and Giridharan [24] proved that $rr(MT(n)) \leq 2n + 1$ and $rr(D(n)) \leq 2n + 2$, where $MT(n)$ and $D(n)$ are Mongolian tent and diamond graphs respectively. In this paper we have estimated the bounds for the radial radio number of certain interconnection networks such as chess board graphs and King's graph.

2. DEFINITIONS AND TERMINOLOGY

In this section we have listed few definitions and results which will be used for proving the theorems. Let u be a vertex of a connected graph G , then the eccentricity of u denoted $e(u)$ is the farthest vertex from u to any other vertex v in G . That is, $e(v) = \max\{d(u, v) \forall v \in V(G)\}$. The radius of the graph G is the minimum

eccentricity of the vertices of G and it is denoted by $\text{rad}(G)$. Pardalos *et al.* [25] defined the following chess board and its related graphs.

An $m \times n$ chessboard graph denoted by $CB(m, n)$ is defined as the Cartesian product $P_m \times P_n$ of paths on m and n vertices respectively. In the literature it is also denoted by $m \times n$ mesh. The mn vertices in $CB(m, n)$ are named as $\{(k, l) \mid l = 1, 2, \dots, m, k = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$. If $m = n$, then the radius of $CB(m, n)$ is $2 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. A $2 \times n$ chessboard graph with $2n$ vertices is also called a ladder graph denoted by L_n . The radius of L_n is $\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$. An $m \times n$ King's graph denoted by $KG(m, n)$ is a graph which is obtained by all legal moves of the king chess piece on a $m \times n$ chessboard $CB(m, n)$. More specifically, it is constructed by the strong product of the paths P_m and P_n . The radius of $KG(m, n)$ is $\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$.

3. MAIN RESULTS

In this section we have obtained the bounds the radial radio number of $2 \times n$ and $n \times n$ chessboard graph separately. Further, we have determined the bounds for the radial radio number of $n \times n$ king's graph.

a) Theorem 1: Let L_n be a ladder graph with $2n$ vertices, then the radial radio number of L_n satisfies

$$rr(L_n) \leq \begin{cases} \frac{n(n+2)}{4} + 1, & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \\ \frac{(n^2-1)}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

Proof: We prove this theorem using two cases based on the value of n , odd or even. Define a radial radio labeling from the vertex set of L_n to the non-negative integers separately for odd and even cases as follows:

1) Case 1: n is even.

Define a labeling from the vertex set of L_n to the non-negative integers as follows:

$$\Upsilon(0, i) = 2(i-1)r - (i-1), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} + 1$$

$$\Upsilon(1, i) = (2i-1)r - (i-1), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} + 1$$

$$\Upsilon(0, \frac{n}{2} + i) = (2i-1)r - (i-1), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} - 1$$

$$\Upsilon(1, \frac{n}{2} + i) = 2(i-1)r - (i-1), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} - 1.$$

See the Figure 1.

Figure 1. A radial radio labeling of ladder graph L_n (n even) which attains the bound

Claim: Υ is a valid radial radio labeling.

Since n is even, the radius of L_n is $\frac{n}{2} + 1$. Therefore, we must prove that $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 2$ for all $u, w \in V(L_n)$

1.1) Case 1.1: Suppose $u \neq w$ belongs to the upper row of L_n , then the following three sub cases can arise.

– Case 1.1.1: If $u = (0, j)$ and $w = (0, k)$, $1 \leq j \neq k \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1$, then $\Upsilon(u) = 2(j-1)r - (j-1)$ and $\Upsilon(w) = 2(k-1)r - (k-1)$. Also, $d(u, w) \geq 1$.

Hence, $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq 1 + |2(j-k)r| \geq 2\frac{n}{2} + 1 \geq \frac{n}{2} + 2$, since $j \neq k$ and $r = \frac{n}{2} + 1$

- Case 1.1.2: If $u = (0, j)$ and $w = (0, k)$, $\frac{n}{2} + 2 \leq j \neq k \leq n$, then $\tau(u) = (2j - 1)r - (j - 1)$ and $\tau(w) = (2k - 1)r - (k - 1)$. Also, $d(u, w) \geq 1$ and $|\tau(u) - \tau(w)| \geq |(2j - 1)r - (2k - 1)r| \geq |2r|$, since $j \neq k$. Hence $|\tau(u) - \tau(w)| + d(u, w) \geq 1 + 2(\frac{n}{2} + 1) > \frac{n}{2} + 2$
 - Case 1.1.3: If $u = (0, j)$, $1 \leq j \leq \frac{n}{2} + 2$ and $w = (0, k)$, $\frac{n}{2} + 2 \leq k \leq n$, then $\tau(u) = 2(j - 1)r - (j - 1)$ and $\tau(w) = (2k - 1)r - (k - 1)$. Here $d(u, w)$ ranges from 1 to $n - 1$. Hence the required condition becomes, $|\tau(u) - \tau(w)| + d(u, w) \geq 1 + |2(j - 1)r - (j - 1) - ((2k - 1)r - (k - 1))| \geq 1 + r = \frac{n}{2} + 2$
- 1.2) Case 1.2: Suppose $u \neq w$ belongs to the lower row of L_n , then we will arrive the same three subcases as in Case 1.1, because the labeling in the first half of the upper row is same as the second half of the lower row and vice versa.
- 1.3) Case 1.3: Let u be a vertex on the upper row and w be a vertex on the lower row.
- Case 1.3.1: If $u = (0, j)$ and $w = (1, k)$, $1 \leq j, k \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1$, then $\tau(u) = 2(j - 1)r - (j - 1)$ and $\tau(w) = (2k - 1)r - (k - 1)$. Since the function values are same, as in Case 1.1.3, $|\tau(u) - \tau(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 2$.
 - Case 1.3.2: Suppose $u = (0, j)$, $1 \leq j \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1$ and $w = (1, k)$, $\frac{n}{2} + 2 \leq k \leq n$, then $\tau(u) = 2(j - 1)r - (j - 1)$ and $\tau(w) = 2(k - 1)r - (k - 1)$.
If $j = k$, then the distance between them is exactly $\frac{n}{2} + 2$, and hence the condition is proved. If $j \neq k$, then $|\tau(u) - \tau(w)| \geq |2(j - 1)r - (j - 1) - (2(k - 1)r - (k - 1))| \geq |2(j - k)r + (j - k)|$ and $d(u, w) \geq 1$. Therefore, $|\tau(u) - \tau(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 2$, since $j \neq k$. The rest of the sub cases also follows the similar proof as that of the previous ones. Hence τ is a valid radial radio labeling. Also, τ received the maximum value $\frac{n(n+2)}{4} + 1$ at the vertex $(1, \frac{n}{2} + 1)$. That is, $\tau(1, \frac{n}{2} + 1) = (2(\frac{n}{2} + 1) - 1)r - (\frac{n}{2} + 1 - 1) = (n + 1)(\frac{n}{2} + 1) - \frac{n}{2} = \frac{n(n+2)}{4} + 1$. Therefore $rr(L_n) \leq \frac{n(n+2)}{4} + 1$, when n is even.

2) Case 2: n is odd

Define a mapping $\tau : V(L_n) \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ as follows: $\tau(0, i) = (2r - 1)(i - 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n+1}{2}$
 $\tau(1, i) = (2i - 1)r - (i - 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n+1}{2}$
 $\tau(0, \frac{n}{2} + i) = (2i - 1)r - (i - 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n-1}{2}$
 $\tau(1, \frac{n}{2} + i) = (2r - 1)(i - 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n-1}{2}$

Figure 2 illustrates the proof of this case. Hence $rr(L_n) \leq \begin{cases} \frac{n(n+2)}{4} + 1, & n \text{ even} \\ \frac{(n^2-1)}{2}, & n \text{ odd} \end{cases}$

Figure 2. A ladder graph L_n (n odd) and its mapping τ

b) Theorem 2: Let $n > 2$ be odd, then the radial radio number of $n \times n$ chessboard graph $CB(n, n)$ satisfies $rr(CB(n, n)) \leq \frac{(n^2-1)(n+1)}{4}$.

Proof: First we partition the vertex set $V(CB(n, n)) = \{(i, j), j = 1, 2, \dots, n, i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ into 4 disjoint sets V_1, V_2, V_3 and V_4 as given below:

$V_1 = \{(i, j) : j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n+1}{2}, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n+1}{2}\}$,
 $V_2 = \{(i, \frac{n+1}{2} + j) : j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n-1}{2}, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n+1}{2}\}$
 $V_3 = \{(\frac{n+1}{2} + i, j) : j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n+1}{2}, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n-1}{2}\}$,
 $V_4 = \{(\frac{n+1}{2} + i, \frac{n+1}{2} + j) : j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n-1}{2}, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n-1}{2}\}$. Clearly $V_i \cap V_j = \emptyset$. Next, we define a mapping $\Upsilon : V(CB(n, n)) \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ as follows:
 $\Upsilon((i, j)) = \frac{(n^2+1)}{2}(i-1) + n(j-1), j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n+1}{2}, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n+1}{2}$
 $\Upsilon((i, \frac{n+1}{2} + j)) = n(j-1) + \left(\frac{n^2+1}\right)(i-1) + \frac{n-1}{2}, j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n-1}{2}, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n+1}{2}$
 $\Upsilon((\frac{n+1}{2} + i, j)) = n(j-1) + \left(\frac{n^2+1}\right)(i-1) + \frac{n-1}{2}, j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n+1}{2}, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n-1}{2}$
 $\Upsilon((\frac{n+1}{2} + i, \frac{n+1}{2} + j)) = \frac{(n^2+1)}{2}(i-1) + n(j-1), j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n-1}{2}, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n-1}{2}$.
 See Figure 3(a).

Now we claim that, the radial radio labeling condition is true for any pair of vertices in $CB(n, n)$. since n is odd, the radius of $M(n, n)$ is $n - 1$. Hence, we must show that $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq n \forall u, w \in V(CB(n, n))$. Let u and w be any two vertices in the chess board graph $CB(n, n)$. Suppose u and w lie in any one of the mutually disjoint sets, then u and w are labelled with a difference at least n . That is, $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| \geq n$. Therefore, there is nothing to verify the radial radio labeling condition in these cases. Hence, we proceed to check the remaining cases.

1) Case 1: Let $u \in V_1$ and $w \in V_2$, then $u = (l, k)$ and $w = (s, \frac{n+1}{2} + t), 1 \leq l, k, s \leq \frac{n+1}{2}, 1 \leq t \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$. Therefore, the corresponding labelings of u and w are $\frac{(n^2+1)}{2}(l-1) + n(k-1)$ and $n(t-1) + \left(\frac{n^2+1}\right)(s-1) + \frac{n-1}{2}$ respectively.

1.1) Case 1.1: If $l = s$ and $k = t$, then the distance between them is exactly $\frac{n+1}{2}$. Therefore $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n+1}{2} + \left| \left(\frac{n^2+1}{2}(l-1) + n(k-1)\right) - \left(n(t-1) + \left(\frac{n^2+1}{2}\right)(s-1) + \frac{n-1}{2}\right) \right| = \frac{n+1}{2} + \frac{n-1}{2} = n$.

1.2) Case 1.2: If $l = s$ and $k = t + 1$, then $d(u, w) = \frac{n-1}{2}$ and $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| = \left| \left(\frac{n^2+1}{2}(l-1) + n(t+1-1)\right) - \left(n(t-1) + \left(\frac{n^2+1}{2}\right)(s-1) + \frac{n-1}{2}\right) \right| \geq \frac{n+1}{2}$. Therefore $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n-1}{2} + \frac{n+1}{2} = n$. Also, for the remaining possibilities in this case, the modulus difference of $\Upsilon(u)$ and $\Upsilon(w)$ is at least $n + \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right) > n$.

Figure 3. A radial radio labeling of (a) CM(7,7) and (b) CM(8,8) which illustrates the mapping

- 2) Case 2: Let $u \in V_1$ and $w \in V_3$, then $u = (l, k)$ and $w = (\frac{n+1}{2} + s, t)$, $1 \leq l, k, t \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$, $1 \leq s \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$. Therefore, $\Upsilon(u) = \frac{(n^2+1)}{2}(l-1) + n(k-1)$ and $\Upsilon(w) = n(t-1) + \left(\frac{n^2+1}{2}\right)(s-1) + \frac{n-1}{2}$ respectively. The rest of the proof in this case is similar to Case 1.
- 3) Case 3: Suppose $u \in V_1$ and $w \in V_4$, then $\Upsilon(u) = \frac{(n^2+1)}{2}(l-1) + n(k-1)$, $1 \leq l, k, \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$ and $\Upsilon(w) = \frac{(n^2+1)}{2}(s-1) + n(t-1)$, $1 \leq s, t \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$, where $u = (l, k)$ and $w = (\frac{n+1}{2} + s, \frac{n+1}{2} + t)$.
- 3.1) Case 3.1: If $l = s$, then $d(u, w) \geq 1$. Hence the radial radio labeling condition becomes, $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) > n$.
- 3.2) Case 3.2: If $s = l + 1$, then $d(u, w) = n - 2$ and $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| \geq \frac{n+1}{2}$. Therefore $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) > n$.
- 3.3) Case 3.3: If $l \neq s$ and $s \neq l + 1$, then $d(u, w) \geq 2$ and $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| \geq n$. Hence $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) > n$.
- 4) Case 4: Let $u \in V_2$ and $w \in V_3$, then $u = (l, \frac{n+1}{2} + k)$ and $w = (\frac{n+1}{2} + s, t)$, $1 \leq l, t \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$, $1 \leq k, s \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$. From the mapping, the values of $\Upsilon(u)$ and $\Upsilon(w)$ are $n(k-1) + \left(\frac{n^2+1}{2}\right)(l-1) + \frac{n-1}{2}$ and $n(t-1) + \left(\frac{n^2+1}{2}\right)(s-1) + \frac{n-1}{2}$ respectively.

If we proceed in the same way as in Case 3, we can easily verify the radial radio labeling condition satisfies for this case also. The remaining cases namely $u \in V_2, w \in V_4$ is similar to case 2 and $u \in V_2, w \in V_4$ is similar to case 1. Thus, we have verified that $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| \geq n \forall u, w \in V(CB(n, n))$. Also, the maximum value of h attains at the vertex $(\frac{n+1}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2})$. Hence, we substitute the values of i and j as $\frac{n+1}{2}$, we get $rr(\Upsilon) = \Upsilon(\frac{n+1}{2}, \frac{n+1}{2}) = \frac{(n^2+1)}{2}(\frac{n+1}{2} - 1) + n(\frac{n+1}{2} - 1) = (\frac{n+1}{2} - 1) \frac{(n+1)^2}{2} = \frac{(n^2-1)(n+1)}{4}$. Thus, $rr(G) \leq \frac{(n^2-1)(n+1)}{4}$.

- c) Theorem 3: For $n > 2$, the radial radio number of $n \times n$ chessboard graph $CB(n, n)$ satisfies $rr(CB(n, n)) \leq \frac{n^2(n+3)}{4}$, whenever n is even.

Proof: Define $\Upsilon : V(CB(n, n)) \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon((i, j)) &= \frac{n(n+1)}{2}(i-1) + n(j-1), j = 1, 2 \dots n, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n}{2} \\ \Upsilon((\frac{n}{2} + 1 + i, j)) &= \frac{n(n+1)}{2}(i-1) + n(j-1) + \frac{n}{2} + 1, j = 1, 2 \dots n, i = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n}{2} - 1 \\ \Upsilon((\frac{n}{2} + 1, j)) &= n(j-1) + \frac{n^2(n+1)}{4}, j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n}{2} + 1 \\ \Upsilon((\frac{n}{2} + 1, \frac{n+1}{2} + j)) &= n(j-1) + 1, j = 1, 2 \dots \frac{n}{2} - 1. \text{ See Figure 3(b).} \end{aligned}$$

Since n is even, the radius of $CB(n, n)$ is n . Hence as in Theorem 3, we can easily verify that $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq n + 1$ holds for every pair of vertices $u, w \in V(CB(n, n))$. Also, the vertex $(\frac{n}{2} + 1, \frac{n}{2} + 1)$ attains the maximum value under the mapping Υ . Therefore, $\Upsilon((\frac{n}{2} + 1, \frac{n}{2} + 1)) = n(\frac{n}{2} + 1 - 1) + \frac{n^2(n+1)}{4} = \frac{n^2(n+3)}{4}$. Hence $rr(CBM(n, n)) \leq \frac{n^2(n+3)}{4}$, whenever n is even.

- d) Theorem 4: Let n be even. Then for the king's graph $KG(n, n)$ satisfies $rr(KG(n, n)) \leq \frac{n^2}{4} + (\frac{n}{2})((n-1)(\frac{n}{2}-1) + 2) - 2, n > 2$.

Proof: Define a mapping $\Upsilon : V(KG(n, n)) \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon(i, 1) &= (i-1)\left(\frac{n}{2}\right), i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} + 1, \\ \Upsilon(\frac{n}{2} + 1 + i, 1) &= (i-1)\left(\frac{n}{2}\right), i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} - 1, \\ \Upsilon(i, \frac{n}{2} + 1) &= i\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} + 1, \\ \Upsilon(\frac{n}{2} + 1 + i, \frac{n}{2} + 1) &= i\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} - 1, \\ \Upsilon(i, j + 1) &= \frac{n^2}{4} + \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)((i-1) + (n-1)(j-1)) + j, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} - 1, \\ \Upsilon(i, \frac{n}{2} + j + 1) &= \frac{n^2}{4} + \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)((i-1) + (n-1)(j-1) + 1) + j - 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2} - 1. \end{aligned}$$

See the Figure 4(a). As the radius of $KG(n, n)$ is $\frac{n}{2}$, we must verify the radial radio labeling condition $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq 1 + \frac{n}{2} \forall u, w \in V(KG(n, n))$

- 1) Case 1: Suppose that u and w are of the form $(s, \frac{n}{2} + 1)$ and $(t, \frac{n}{2} + 1)$ where $1 \leq s \neq t \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1$. Then $\Upsilon(s, \frac{n}{2} + 1) = (\frac{n}{2})s$, $\Upsilon(t, \frac{n}{2} + 1) = (\frac{n}{2})t$ and $d(u, w) > 0$. Consequently $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq |(\frac{n}{2})(s - t)| + 1 \geq \frac{n}{2} + 1$
- 2) Case 2: Let us take $u = (\frac{n}{2} + s, \frac{n}{2} + 1)$ and $w = (\frac{n}{2} + t, \frac{n}{2} + 1)$, then $\Upsilon(u) = (\frac{n}{2})s$ and $\Upsilon(w) = (\frac{n}{2})t$, $1 \leq s \neq t \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1$. As $d(u, w) \geq 1$, $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 1$.
- 3) Case 3: Suppose $u = (k, l + 1)$ and $w = (s, t + 1)$, $1 \leq k, s \leq n$, $1 \leq l, t \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1$, then $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| = |(\frac{n^2}{4} + (\frac{n}{2})((k - 1) + (n - 1)(l - 1)) + l) - (\frac{n^2}{4} + (\frac{n}{2})((s - 1) + (n - 1)(t - 1)) + t)|$.
- 3.1) Case 3.1: Allowing $k \neq s$, we get $d(u, w) \geq 1$ and $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| \geq \frac{n}{2}$, which confirm the result.
- 3.2) Case 3.2: If $l \neq t$, then $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| \geq (\frac{n}{2})(n - 1)$ and $d(u, w) > 0$ which verifies $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 1$, since $n > 2$.
- 4) Case 4: Let $u = (k, \frac{n}{2} + l + 1)$ and $w = (s, \frac{n}{2} + t + 1)$, $1 \leq k, s \leq n$, $1 \leq l, t \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1$. If $k \neq s$, then $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| = |(\frac{n^2}{4} + (\frac{n}{2})((k - 1) + (n - 1)(l - 1) + 1) + l - 1) - (\frac{n^2}{4} + (\frac{n}{2})((s - 1) + (n - 1)(t - 1) + 1) + t - 1)| \geq \frac{n}{2}$. Again, $l \neq t$ implies that $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| \geq (\frac{n}{2})(n - 1)$. Since $d(u, w) \geq 1$, whence in both the possibilities, the condition $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 1$ is verified.
- 5) Case 5: Suppose $u = (k, 1)$ of $(\frac{n}{2} + 1 + s, 1)$ and $w = (l, 1)$ or $(\frac{n}{2} + 1 + t, 1)$, then either $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| = 0$ and $d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 1$ or $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| = \frac{n}{2}$ and $d(u, w) \geq 1$. Hence in both chances $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 1$.
- 6) Case 6: Assume $u = (i, 1)$ and $w = (i, \frac{n}{2} + 1)$, $1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} + 1$, then $\Upsilon(u) = (i - 1)(\frac{n}{2})$, $\Upsilon(w) = i(\frac{n}{2}) - 1$ and $d(u, w) \geq 1$. Therefore, $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) \geq \frac{n}{2} + 1$.
- 7) Case 7: If $u = (i, j + 1)$ and $w = (k, \frac{n}{2} + l + 1)$, then $\Upsilon(u) = i(\frac{n}{2}) - 1$ and $\Upsilon(w) = \frac{n^2}{4} + (\frac{n}{2})((k - 1) + (n - 1)(l - 1) + 1) + l - 1$, $1 \leq i, l \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1$, $1 \leq j, k \leq n$. Therefore, $|\Upsilon(u) - \Upsilon(w)| + d(u, w) > \frac{n}{2} + 1$.

Similarly, we can verify the radial radio condition for the rest of the cases. Thus, Υ is a valid radial radio labeling and which attains the maximum label $\frac{n^2}{4} + (\frac{n}{2})((n - 1) + (n - 1)(\frac{n}{2} - 2) + 1) + \frac{n}{2} - 1 = \frac{n^2}{4} + (\frac{n}{2})((n - 1)(\frac{n}{2} - 1) + 2) - 2$ for the vertex (n, n) . Thus $rr(KG(n, n)) \leq n^2/4 + (n/2)((n - 1)(n/2 - 1) + 2) - 2, n > 2$.

- e) Theorem 5: Let n be odd. Then the radial radio number of $KG(n, n)$ satisfies $rr(KG(n, n)) \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor (\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1) + \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor ((n - 1) \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1), n > 2$.

Proof: Define a mapping $\Upsilon : V(KG(n, n)) \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ as follows:

$$\Upsilon(i, 1) = (i - 1) \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor, i = 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor,$$

$$\Upsilon(\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + i, 1) = (i - 1) \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor, i = 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor,$$

$$\Upsilon(i, \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1) = i \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor,$$

$$\Upsilon(\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + i, \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1) = i \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor,$$

$$\Upsilon(i, j + 1) = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor (\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1) + \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor ((i - 1) + (n - 1)(j - 1)) + j, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor,$$

$$\Upsilon(i, \frac{n}{2} + j + 1) = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor (\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1) + \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor ((i - 1) + (n - 1)(j - 1) + 1) + j, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1.$$

See the Figure 4(b). The rest of the proof is omitted.

Figure 4. A radial radio labeling of $KG(n,n)$ for (a) $n = 6$ and (b) $n = 7$ which illustrates the mapping

4. CONCLUSION

The upper bounds for the radial radio number of chess board graphs $CB(m, n)$ for $m = 2, n$ and the King's graph $KG(m, n)$ for $m = n (n > 2)$ has been investigated in this research work. For $m \neq n (n > 2)$, $CB(m, n)$ and $KG(m, n)$ is still an open problem. Future this research can be extended to identify higher dimensional networks and study the same radial radio number problem due to its application to telecommunication networks.

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